

Transferability of Alzheimer's Disease Polygenic Risk Scores derived from Europeans across multiple genetic ancestries.

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Analysis Plan

- 1- Check the data and its quality (1st script)
- 2- Compute the GRS (1st script)
- 3- Provide a quick quality check of the covariate file (2nd script)
- 4- Perform the association studies, stratification analyses and the quantile association (2nd script)
- 5- Provide the results (outputs of script 1 and 2) and the list of authors.

Data Recommendations:

To run the 2 scripts, you will need, 1- your vcf or bcf file with the dosages or the genotypes of your samples, and 2- a "covariate file", containing the AD status, and the covariates you used in your association studies.

- Required format to run the first script is vcf, vcf.gz or bcf

Two types of data are accepted: Genotyping/Imputed data and WGS data.

It is highly recommended to extract the variants of interest from your vcf/bcf before running the scripts. To perform the extraction, a list of the variants of interest and their related information is provided with the two scripts, in the file AD_GRS_variant_information_for_Multiancestry.txt. Some wanted SNPs could be multi-allelic. If that's the case in your cohort, you will have to split them into several bi-allelic SNPs prior to the computation of the GRS. If you need assistance to extract or split them, please, contact me. The more SNPs are extracted, the more accurate the association will be.

The SNP ID is in the format chromosome:position:reference_allele:alternate_allele based on the GRCh38/hg38 assembly

- Genotyping/Imputed data:

Please transmit your pre-imputation and post-imputation QC procedure.

- 1- Imputation panel: TOPMed or other reference panel according to the ancestry of the cohort in GRCh38/hg38 assembly.
- 2- If the imputation is in GRCh37/hg19 (e.g. HRC), please contact me and I will provide you with the variants' list in GRCh37/hg19 coordinates and proxy variants, when available.
- 3- Select SNPs with an imputation quality (Rsqr) > 0.3, no other filtering must be performed such as minor allele frequency.
- 4- Dosages (DS) info is preferred over Genotypes (GT) to take into account the uncertainty. The Dosage information (FORMAT=DS in the vcf file) is used to compute the GRS. Below is an example of a header vcf line where Dosage information is found.
FORMAT=<ID=DS,Number=1,Type=Float,Description="Estimated Alternate Allele Dosage : [P(0/1)+2*P(1/1)]">

- WGS data

Nothing to specify, should have passed your QC. Please, transmit your QC procedure.

- Samples:

- exclude samples used in Bellenguez, *et al*, Nature Genetics 2022a, if any
- exclude related samples
- include Caucasians and/or other genetic ancestries, admixed samples, etc
- Phenotype: Alzheimer's Disease status (cases=1, controls=0)

NB: In particular cases, we could extend to Alzheimer's Disease Related Diseases, Dementia, if the cohorts are small. Please contact me, in such a case.

- use samples passing your Quality control and please provide your quality control procedure at the same time as the results.
- remove samples with at least 1 missing SNP in our list, otherwise, the script 1 will do it automatically.

1- Computation of GRS

Script1: [compute_raw_PGS.pl](#)

Variants file: AD_GRS_variant_information_for_Multiancestry.txt or
[genetic_ancestry_specific_variant_file.txt](#)

Usage: perl [compute_raw_PGS.pl](#) <path_to_bcftools> <input_file.vcf.gz> <variant_file>
<output_file>

Example: perl compute_GRS_Multiancestry.pl bcftools-1.11/bcftools BZL.vcf.gz
AD_GRS_variant_information_for_Multiancestry.txt BZL_GRS.txt

This script relies on the perl environment. If you have any questions about it (installation for instance if not available), please contact me

This script computes the GRS in your samples according to the variants and their related beta, provided in the variants file. The script checks for the reference and alternate alleles.

You will find 4 output files: 1) output_file.log, containing the list of SNPs tested and other information. We will need you provide this file. 2) output_file containing per sample 3 different GRSs (grs_83, grs_apoe, grs_apoe_only). 3) output_file.sampleexcluded.txt listing samples with at least one missing genotype or dosage and thus removed from the output_file. 4) output_file.freqforQC.txt reporting the frequencies of the variant in your study. We will check them for large differences compared to reference panels.

We invite you to have a look at the log file and the excluded samples before sending final results to us. We will need at least the output_file.log and output_file.freqforQC.txt. We will appreciate if you provide also the output_file.

2- Association analyses

Script2: *association_test_quantiles_PGS_Multiancestry.R*

Usage:

Rscript *association_test_quantiles_PGS_Multiancestry.R* <GRS_outputfile> <COV_clinic_file>
<OUTPUT_file_prefix> <COVARIATE_list>

Example: Rscript *association_test_quantiles_GRS_Multiancestry.R* BZL_GRS.txt BZL_covariates.txt
BZL_GRS_results.txt PC1,PC2,PC4,genotyping_center,SEX,AGE,APOE4,APOE2,CEU,NAM,AFR

NB: the covariates are coma separated only, in the command line. The fields of the COV_clinic_file are tabulation separated.

This script relies on the R environment. Moreover, this script uses different packages which need to be installed: 'data.table', 'ggplot2', 'plyr', 'gridExtra', 'reshape2', 'dplyr', 'stringr', 'pROC', 'DescTools', 'caret', 'rcompanion'. If you have any questions about it (installation of R itself or installation of the needed packages), please contact me.

The script 2 computes the different associations of GRSs according to the status, and the covariates provided. It performs also quantile regressions, stratification analyses and interaction analyses, according to the different covariates available. This script also plots the distributions of age, sex and grs in your study.

Importantly, the covariate file should contain the following columns:

Mandatory columns:

IID: the IID should corresponds to the sample ID encoded in the vcf/bcf file.

AD_status: should be 0 for controls and 1 for cases.

Both column names are in upper case.

The optional columns are:

the Principal Components of the population structure, the number of APOE4 alleles, the number of APOE2 alleles, the APOE_STATUS, the age, the sex, and if admixed samples, the %CEU, %NAM, %AFR, and additional covariates if needed (e.g. batch). If a covariate should be considered as a factor in the analysis (such as genotyping centers, batches, etc), encode them with characters rather than numbers. **We are asking to use as much as possible, all these covariates.** However, if too many samples are removed because of missing information, for a single covariate, please consider removing this covariate from the analysis.

For classical covariates, name them in uppercase.

if SEX, column name "SEX", female: 2, male: 1

if AGE, column name "AGE", age-at-last-exam for controls, age-at-onset for cases, or what is more relevant in your cohort. If not age-at-onset, please let us know which age you used.

if APOE2, and or APOE4, column names "APOE2", "APOE4", number of APOE2 alleles, number of APOE4 alleles (values: 0,1,2). If you have APOE2 and APOE4 imputed, please check with the APOE2 and APOE4 status when available. If you see discrepancies, remove the sample.

if APOE_STATUS (values: 22,23,33,43,44,42), column names "APOE_STATUS".

If your cohort includes admixed samples, please run the script including CEU,AFR,NAM, in the command line, if you have this information.

The column names reporting the percentages of the different genetic ancestries, should be "CEU", "AFR" and "NAM". If other genetic ancestries, please contact me.

Please remove samples with missing values for the covariate(s) selected

The principal outputs of the script 2 are:

- the distribution plots
- OUTPUT_file_prefix_studydescription.txt,
- OUTPUT_file_prefix_firstsetassoc.txt,
- OUTPUT_file_prefix_interactionanalyses.txt,
- OUTPUT_file_prefix_stratifiedanalyses.txt,
- OUTPUT_file_prefix_percentiles.txt

We will mostly need these files.

Thank you very much for your collaboration!

If you have technical or other questions, do not hesitate to contact me.

Contacts:

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Reference:

Bellenguez, *et al.* "New insights into the genetic etiology of Alzheimer's disease and related dementias." *Nature Genetics* 2022